

EURODINAME III - An International Symposium on Dynamic
Problems of Mechanics
June 8-11, 2026 - Giens Peninsula, FR

EURODINAME-2026-12939

ACOUSTIC WAVE PROPAGATION PATTERNS IN HYPERBOLIC LATTICES

Afonso W. Nunes

University of Campinas, School of Mechanical Engineering, Campinas, São Paulo, Brazil
afonsown@unicamp.br

Danilo Beli

Eindhoven University of Technology, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Eindhoven, Netherlands
beli.danilo@gmail.com

Rubén Picó

Instituto de Investigación para la Gestión Integrada de Zonas Costeras, Universitat Politècnica de Valencia, Gandia, Spain
rpico@upv.edu.es

J. Roberto F. Arruda

University of Campinas, School of Mechanical Engineering, Campinas, São Paulo, Brazil
arruda@fem.unicamp.br

Abstract. *Sonic crystals based on hyperbolic geometry are a recent and promising branch of acoustic metamaterial studies. The literature on the subject explores wave localization phenomena, super-resolution imaging, and robustness to defects, in addition to wave phenomena that are well known from traditional acoustic metamaterials. In brief, these hyperbolic metamaterials are constructed according to rules of hyperbolic geometry, enabling negative-curvature spaces that offer infinite possibilities for regular tessellations of periodic lattices. These tessellations enable the positioning of any polygonal arrangement without spatial gaps, thereby opening up new possibilities of periodic cell-placing configurations that cannot be assessed in conventional periodic lattices defined in Euclidean space. This work explores this topic by investigating how acoustic waves propagate in sonic crystals based upon hyperbolic lattices. To achieve this, we assess hyperbolic lattices for sonic crystals via numerical simulations. These results allow insights into the potential applications for noise control.*

Keywords: *Hyperbolic Sonic Crystals, Acoustic Metamaterials, Wave Manipulation, Hyperbolic Geometry*

1. INTRODUCTION

Performance demands on engineering structures have driven the development of materials designed to overcome intrinsic limitations of traditional ones, such as acoustic metamaterials and sonic crystals for advanced wave control (Maldovan, 2013; Landy *et al.*, 2008; Shelby *et al.*, 2001; Smith *et al.*, 2000). Sonic crystals use periodicity to induce bandgap formation by the Bragg effect, thus preventing wave propagation at specific frequencies, while self-collimation and negative refraction are also attainable (Martínez-Sala *et al.*, 1995; Gupta, 2014; Soliveres *et al.*, 2009; Feng *et al.*, 2005). Alternatively, metamaterials can operate in the subwavelength regime, achieving wave attenuation, wave beaming and diffraction for directionality, robustness against defects, cloaking for acoustic invisibility, and adaptive structures for tunable dynamics (Cummer *et al.*, 2016; Gao *et al.*, 2022; Xie *et al.*, 2014; Beli *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2011; Norris, 2008). Many of these designs achieve their desired dynamic effects by leveraging spatial periodicity, either by maintaining strict geometric arrangements or by deliberately breaking them to induce topological effects (Lee *et al.*, 2010; Kadic *et al.*, 2019; Airoidi and Ruzzene, 2011; Popa and Cummer, 2014; Gliozzi *et al.*, 2019; Feng *et al.*, 2005).

The architecture of periodic media arises from underlying tessellations, namely geometric arrangements of polygons that tile surfaces or volumes without gaps or overlaps (Gao *et al.*, 2023; Williams, 1979). In standard Euclidean geometry, these tessellations are constrained to only a few configurations, such as the meeting of four squares or two octagons

and a square at each vertex (Johnson, 2013). Meanwhile, transitioning to non-Euclidean spaces significantly relaxes the constraints on constructing tessellations; specifically, the negative curvature of hyperbolic spaces permits an infinite variety of polygonal configurations (Ryan, 1986; Coxeter, 1998; Greenberg, 2008). This flexibility arises because negative curvature results in smaller interior angles in polygons than in their Euclidean counterparts. Consequently, the more negatively curved the space, the more polygons can be fit around a point, enabling configurations that are geometrically impossible in a flat Euclidean plane.

While the vast majority of metamaterial research has been consolidated within the Euclidean framework, hyperbolic lattice geometries have recently provided unprecedented modal densities and topologically nontrivial wave states (Kollár *et al.*, 2019; Liu *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2022; Bienias *et al.*, 2022). In the context of mechanical waves, these lattices induce modal localization, suggesting significant potential for optimizing energy harvesting and providing localized structural protection against vibration transmission (Ruzzene *et al.*, 2021; Patino *et al.*, 2024, 2025). However, despite these advances in structural dynamics, the acoustic implications of hyperbolic tessellations remain largely unexplored. Sharifi Moghaddam *et al.* (2024) constructed regular lattices of 3D hyperbolic-shaped insertions to improve energy harvesting, although still based on Euclidean arrangements. Specifically, there is no systematic research investigating the relationship between space curvature and dynamic responses in acoustic media.

This work proposes the concept of Hyperbolic Sonic Crystals (HSCs) and investigates the impact of hyperbolic curvature on acoustic wave propagation in projected lattice geometries. For this purpose, Section 2. defines the geometric framework of HSCs derived from hyperbolic lattices and examines the relevant properties of hyperbolic space for their design. Section 3. details the investigation setups and discusses the observed wave dynamic effects. Finally, Section 4. presents the concluding remarks and future perspectives of this work.

2. HYPERBOLIC LATTICES AND HYPERBOLIC SONIC CRYSTALS

Hyperbolic geometry originates from the negation of Euclid’s fifth postulate. Specifically, it employs the Lobachevsky postulate to assert that more than one parallel line can be drawn through a point external to another line, in contrast to the unique parallel in Euclidean geometry. This mathematical foundation enables the definition of curved spaces, where those characterized by negative Gaussian curvature are labeled as hyperbolic (Bonola, 1955; Coxeter, 1998). Hyperbolic spaces cannot be fully visualized within Euclidean environments, so models represent the non-Euclidean rules visually using the language of Euclidean geometry. The Poincaré disk model, whose mapping is illustrated in Fig. 1 (a), is a representation that projects the infinite hyperbolic plane onto a finite flat disk, while preserving the original space angles (Éric Charpentier *et al.*, 2010).

Figure 1: Hyperbolic surface and tessellations

The construction of hyperbolic lattice structures can arise from tilings within this modeled disk. The tiling represented in Fig. 1 (b) follows the Schläfli notation $\{p, q\}$, where q regular p sided polygons meet at each vertex, covering the infinite space. In this example, the notation $\{4, 5\}$ describes a configuration with five squares at each vertex (Coxeter, 2012). When truncating these infinite polygons to form a finite lattice, the Schläfli notation can be adapted to explicitly include the number of polygon generations, as shown in Fig. 1 (c) for the tessellation $\{4, 5\}$ with 3 generations, denoting the finite hyperbolic lattice by $\{4, 5, 3\}$.

The design of HSCs is based on hyperbolic tessellations mapped onto the Poincaré disk with circular scatterers placed at the geometric centers of each polygon. The scatterer areas are scaled proportionally to the areas of their host limiting polygons, as they would be if placed over the hyperbolic surface. This approach ensures that the HSC uses a uniform

local filling fraction (LFF), defined as the ratio of the areas of each circular scatterer and its corresponding host polygon in the underlying tessellation, mapped onto the Poincaré disk, both evaluated consistently under the Euclidean metric. This configuration is illustrated in Fig. 1 (d), with colored scatterers and the remaining region filled with air.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical study uses acoustic simulations in COMSOL Multiphysics 6.3, with air at standard conditions (20°C and 1 atm), a density of 1.2925 kg/m³, and a speed of sound of 331.29 m/s. The excitation is provided by a monopole point source placed at the geometric center of the HSCs with a flow rate of 1 m²/s. The HSCs occupy a circle of radius 1 m within the acoustic domain. The scatterers are modeled as hard boundaries, while the outer domain boundaries are perfectly matched layers to prevent waves from reflecting back into the system. The frequency analysis is performed from 0 to 4 kHz for all HSCs. The dynamics are characterized by the insertion loss (IL), defined as the attenuation induced by the crystal relative to free propagation, and by the acoustic frequency response functions (FRF), which quantify the pressure response to monopole excitation at the center of the HSC, at the origin of the Poincaré disk.

The investigation proceeds through three case studies. Case A considers a configuration with constant hyperbolic curvature, maintaining a fixed number of polygon sides and vertices while varying the number of generations. This approach allows exploring how the addition of scatterers, following rules of hyperbolic tessellations, influences the resulting wave dynamics. Case B fixes the number of generations and varies the hyperbolic curvature, first by altering the number of polygon sides and subsequently the number of polygons per vertex. This case investigates the relation between wave dynamics and the spatial curvature. Finally, Case C fixes the hyperbolic tessellation serving as the basis for the investigated HSCs and varies the LFF to examine the response's sensitivity to the proportional size of the scatterers.

3.1 Case A

The geometric arrangements for fixed-curvature HSCs based on the tessellation $\{3, 7\}$ with 1 to 5 generations are illustrated in Fig. 2. Here, the ratio of tessellated polygons to inclusion areas is 40%, namely the LFF. As shown by the corresponding IL colormaps in Fig. 3, the wide attenuation zones centered around 0.5 kHz become more pronounced as the number of generations increases. Furthermore, attenuation zones, such as those at 2.66 and 3.82 kHz, broaden significantly. These effects are consistently observed in the mean acoustic FRFs, which average the response across all points along the HSC's border from 0 to 180°, with angles conventionally represented in the polar plane. The increase in the number of generations also induces the formation of secondary attenuation zones, arising from the smaller introduced scatterers.

Figure 2: HSCs based on heptagonal tessellations of triangles ($\{3, 7, n\}$) with different generations, LFF 40%

In addition to the sound attenuation properties, these HSCs exhibit significant acoustic pressure localization at particular frequencies. Examples of localization at the highest (outer) generation of different HSCs are shown in Fig. 4. As generations increase, new resonances appear while those from previous generations are largely preserved. However, in some cases, a degeneracy occurs, as observed around 1 kHz when transitioning from $\{3, 7, 2\}$ to $\{3, 7, 3\}$. The localization at the lowest (inner) generations is shown in Fig. 5. Such localization phenomena arise at multiple frequencies across the spectrum and can involve several generations simultaneously. As the generation increases, additional resonant modes emerge while those identified in previous generations persist, resulting in a cumulative modal structure. Moreover, the resulting acoustic vibration patterns exhibit radial and azimuthal symmetries, with characteristics that depend on both the excitation frequency and the specific HSC geometry.

3.2 Case B

An increase in the number of polygon sides or the number of polygons per vertex requires a higher degree of spatial curvature to embed the regular tessellation. To investigate the effect of curvature on wave dynamics, Fig. 6 shows crystals derived from tessellations containing four polygons per vertex, starting with the zero-curvature sonic crystal in (a), which corresponds to the classical Euclidean SC. Increasing the number of polygon sides in the tessellations results in negative-curvature HSCs. The chosen LFF is 50%.

Figure 3: IL and spatial mean acoustic FRF for $\{3, 7, n\}$, LFF 40%

Figure 4: Acoustic pressure localization at the n th generation for $\{3, 7, n\}$, LFF 40%

Figure 5: Acoustic pressure localization along generations for $\{3, 7, 5\}$, LFF 40%

As the number of polygon sides increases in Fig. 7, attenuation zones become less pronounced and shift to lower frequencies. This occurs because more curved spaces imply more distant inclusions relative to the center of the Poincaré disk. Compared to the standard Euclidean sonic crystal, HSCs exhibit narrower, but usually more intense, localized attenuation. This leads to an FRF with more peaks than for $\{4, 4, 4\}$, a consequence of the rich and complex dynamics inherent to HSCs.

Distinctive acoustic field pressure patterns can be achieved by varying the spatial curvature. For that, the crystals shown in Fig. 8 are formed by increasing the number of squares per vertex in tessellations. At specific resonance frequencies, their geometric arrangements induce pressure fields that reproduce the polygonal arrangement pattern, as illustrated in Fig. 9. This phenomenon demonstrates that the geometrical properties of the hyperbolic lattice can shape the spatial organization of energy.

Figure 6: HSCs based on p -gonal tessellations ($\{p, 4, 4\}$), LFF 50%

Figure 7: IL and spatial mean acoustic FRF for $\{p, 4, 4\}$, LFF 50%

Figure 8: HSCs based on tetragonal tessellations of polygons with q sides ($\{4, q, 3\}$), LFF 30%

3.3 Case C

This final study examines HSCs with fixed spatial curvature and number of generations, and varies the LFFs according to the $\{5, 4, 3\}$ pentagonal tessellation, as shown in Fig. 10. As illustrated by the IL colormaps and mean acoustic FRFs in Fig. 11, increasing the LFF from 30% to 70% significantly modifies the crystal wave dynamics. Higher LFFs reduce the effective inter-scatterer spacing, broadening and shifting the attenuation zones upward in frequency. This shift is particularly evident in the lower gap appearing at 1.5 kHz for LFF 30% that transitions to 2.5 kHz for LFF 70%, becoming more significant for the attenuation dynamics. This enhancement, however, comes at the expense of increased acoustic impedance; higher LFFs imply greater airflow blocking.

(a) $\{4, 4, 3\}$, 3336 Hz (b) $\{4, 5, 3\}$, 2824 Hz (c) $\{4, 6, 3\}$, 2950 Hz (d) $\{4, 7, 3\}$, 3158 Hz (e) $\{4, 8, 3\}$, 3342 Hz

Figure 9: Pressure patterns at the first two generations for $\{4, q, 3\}$, LFF 30%

(a) LFF 30% (b) LFF 40% (c) LFF 50% (d) LFF 60% (e) LFF 70%

Figure 10: HSCs based on tetragonal tessellations of pentagons $\{5, 4, 3\}$ with different LFFs

Figure 11: IL and spatial mean acoustic FRF for $\{5, 4, 3\}$ with different LFFs

4. FINAL REMARKS

This work proposes the concept of hyperbolic sonic crystals mapped onto the Poincaré disk and analyzes their effects on acoustic wave propagation. The infinite variety of regular hyperbolic tessellations offers great flexibility in choosing geometric parameters, such as the number of subsequent subdivisions by polygon sides or per vertex, while preserving many symmetries and overall periodicity. Linked to such parameters is the space curvature, which determines the arrangement of the corresponding tessellations and directly influences the propagation of acoustic waves.

The investigation across three case studies identified acoustic attenuation zones, pattern formation, and localization effects. Increasing the number of polygon generations enhances structural complexity while deepening and broadening attenuation zones. From this setup, the progressive addition of generations allows independent study of the effects of each

generation of scatterers, and then selecting the number of generations necessary to achieve the desired wave effects.

Higher curvature shifts attenuation zones toward lower frequencies and allows the formation of unique polygonal pressure patterns at specific resonance frequencies that mimic the crystal geometric arrangements. The ratio of the areas of the scatterers to those of the tessellated polygons is a critical parameter for enhancing the wave-dynamic effects of HSCs. While higher LFFs broaden attenuation zones and shift them to higher frequencies, they also increase acoustic impedance and airflow blocking.

Potential applications of HSCs might address noise barriers, engineered as highly effective filters at particular frequencies, or broaden frequency attenuation by increasing the number of generations. In the field of acoustic energy harvesting, the strong, localized pressure fields observed in hyperbolic lattices can be used to concentrate acoustic energy at specific locations, improving the efficiency of the harvesting system. Future studies should address experimental validation. Finally, extending this research into three-dimensional hyperbolic manifolds could reveal more complex and unusual wave phenomena for advanced wave manipulation in acoustics.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was financed, in part, by the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP), Brasil. Process Numbers 2018/15894-0, 2024/23127-0, and 2025/03796-8. This research was also developed under grant PID2022-138321NBC22 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and ERDF/EU.

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